

Ben ELUGBE and Firmin AHOUA

**Typologie et documentation
des langues en Afrique de l'Ouest**

**Language Typology and Documentaton
in West Africa**

**Les actes du 27ème Congrès de la Société de Linguistique de l'Afrique de l'Ouest (SLAO)
Université de Cocody, Abidjan, du 14 au 20 Août 2011**

**Proceedings of the 27th West African Linguistics Congress (WALS)
University of Cocody, Abidjan, from August 14th to 20th 2011**

Editors: Ben ELUGBE and Firmin AHOUA

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*Ben Elugbe
2016*

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COMPARATIVE AKEDOID AND WEST BENUE-CONGO

Ben Elugbe

University of Ibadan, NIGERIA

1. KWA AND BENUE-CONGO

For a long time, the received classification of Kwa and Benue-Congo was that of Greenberg 1963, revised in 1966. Greenberg's Kwa branch of the Niger-Congo Phylum extended from the Ivory Coast in the West to the Benue and Cross River valleys in south-eastern Nigeria. Greenberg himself cast doubt on the integrity of Kwa and Benue-Congo as separate branches within Niger-Congo when he wrote that genuine doubts existed as to the separateness of Kwa and Benue-Congo (1966: 39).

Greenberg's Kwa contained eight subgroups, numbered (a) to (h):

- a. Kru,
- b. Akan, etc.,
- c. Yoruba,
- d. Nupe, Gbari (Gwari), Igbirra (Ebira), Gade,
- e. Bini (Edo), Ishan (Esan), Kukuruku (Yekhee (Etsako)), Sobo (Urhobo),
- f. Idoma, Agatu, Iyala,
- g. Ibo (Igbo), and
- h. Ijo.

Of these, c-h were labelled Eastern Kwa by Armstrong 1967. All the languages in this putative or purely geographic nomenclature are in Nigeria – with the exception of the cross-border and discontinuous parts of Yoruba in the Republics of Benin and Togo.

In general, there were supposed to be phonological and morphological characteristics that were typical Kwa, especially Eastern Kwa, and separated it from Benue-Congo. Kwa stems were monosyllabic, the syllables being CV and V, with no closed syllables and no consonant clusters. Verbs typically started with consonants while nouns started with vowels which were noun prefixes attached to the noun stems. In some of the (Eastern) Kwa languages, these prefixes served a singular/plural purpose. The complex noun class systems so distinctive in Bantu and Bantoid in Benue-Congo were missing. Verbal extensions were also missing. With this kind of archetype, the simple morphology of Kwa, with its monosyllabic and mono-morphemic root/stem, was separated from the complex morphology of Benue-Congo (see Westerman and Bryan 1952).

These are clearly typological characteristics which were not backed up with any support from comparison and reconstruction. It is not surprising, therefore, to learn that scholars such as William Welmers, Roger Wescott, Robert Armstrong, and others had expressed doubts 'as to whether Kwa is really a distinct group (from Benue-Congo) within Niger-Congo' (Stewart 1976, quoting Greenberg 1963b). De Wolf 1971 said that he believed that the so-called Togo-Remnant languages, classified within Kwa, are 'definitely part of Benue-Congo' (p. 180).

Based on this assault on the status of Kwa, it is understandable that its history should show that there have been various attempts to unite it with Benue-Congo. Givón 1975 used the term Benue-Kwa, which was also used by Elugbe and Williamson 1977. Bennet and Sterk 1977 said that they considered 'Benue-Kwa' but that they thought that it still reminded one of the dividing line that they believed did not exist between Kwa and Benue-Congo. They proposed Eastern South-Central Niger-Congo (ESCNC). This ESCNC is approximately Greenberg's eastern Kwa and Benue-Congo – i.e. Benue-Kwa definitely without Kru and with or without Ijo. But in trying to find a new name and definition, Stewart had preceded Bennett and Sterk in his Volta-Congo hypothesis, put forward in his inaugural lecture of 1976 at the University of Leiden in Holland. By 1989, in the influential book *The Niger-Congo languages*, edited by John Bendor-Samuel, the new terms (New) Kwa and (New) Benue-Congo emerged. The (New) Kwa chapter was written by Stewart, who would later regret it (personal communication). I don't know if he should have worried because the (New) Kwa and the (New) Benue-Congo were placed within his Volta-Congo family. The New Kwa was without the extreme west and east members of Greenberg's Kwa – Kru and Ijo respectively. It was also without eastern Kwa, which had been transferred to Benue-Congo.

Finally, Williamson and Blench (2000) returned to some kind of division within the new Benue-Congo by talking about West Benue-Congo (WBC) and East Benue-Congo (EBC). Thus, the division which Bennett and Sterk wanted to forget is simply not going away.

In a recent study, Ohiri-Aniche (2004) tried to see whether some historical developments in stem-initial consonants in Igbooid of WBC could be identified in Lower Cross of East Benue-Congo and used to link the two groups, and so imply either that the East-West distinction is unnecessary or that the dividing line is currently at the wrong place. She said that her finding supported a dividing line between Igbooid (WBC) and Lower Cross (EBC).

In the last ten years, many small languages of the area southwest of the Niger-Benue confluence have become better known. More data have become available and we now know the towns and villages where many hitherto unknown languages are spoken. A number of studies are now available, such as Abiodun 2001 on AIKA, the so-called Ukaan; Akinyemi 2002 on Akokoid, showing clearly that Ahanoid must be classified outside Akokoid; Elugbe 2002 on the tone system of Akpes; Chido 2002 on a proposed orthography for the Iluen dialect of Akpes; and Atoyebi's reference grammar of Ọkọ (2010). Earlier in 1983, Ibrahim had done a comparative study of the Akpes dialects. And as against Greenberg's time, we now have in-depth studies of virtually all the big groups in WBC: Elugbe 1973, 1989 (Edoid); Akinkugbe 1978 (Yoruboid); Armstrong 1983 (Idomoid); Bankale 2006 (Nupoid and Ebiroid). All these are in addition to what was said of each of these larger groups in Bendor-Samuel 1989.

In spite of this phenomenal increase in our knowledge of WBC, many challenges remain, which refuse to dissipate or disappear. These are the issues in West

Benue-Congo and they will be identified and discussed very briefly in the next section.

2. THE ISSUES

The current composition of West Benue-Congo is as follows:

- Yoruboid (Yoruba, Işekiri, Igala),
- Akokoid (the Qwɔn dialects of Oke-Agbe, Arigidi, Erushu, Urɔ, Igashi, Oyin),
- Ahanoid (Ahan (Omuo)-Uwu (Ayer)),
- Akedoid (Edoid plus Akpes and the AIKA dialect cluster),
- Okoid (Okɔ of Ogori and Osanyen of Magongo),
- Nupoid (Nupe, Gwari, Gade),
- Ebiroid (Ebira Kwoto, Ebira (Okene, etc., of Kogi State, and Eṭuṅo of Igarra in Edo State),
- Igboïd (Igbo and closely related languages/dialects), and
- Idomoid (Yatye, Idoma, Igede, Yala) (see Map 1, which does not show Okoid (Ogori) and Ahanoid).

The decidedly small languages of Ahanoid, Akokoid, and Okoid, as well as Akpes and AIKA of Akedoid, are inside the general area of Ebiroid, Akokoid, and the northern fringes of Yoruboid and Akedoid.

2.1 Eastern Kwa or West Benue-Congo?

The first issue is reflected in the title of this subsection. The question has to be posed and answered. We saw above that the status of Kwa as an autonomous branch of Niger-Congo was much challenged. This was because Kwa and Benue-Congo share a number of similarities and are seen as close. However, the absence of noun class systems similar to the Bantu and Bantoid ones was a factor in separating Kwa and Benue-Congo in the first instance. Ironically, the discovery of vibrant noun class systems in Oloma and other Edoid languages as well as in Gade of Nupoid were partly responsible for bringing Eastern Kwa into Benue-Congo. It was not the typological use that had been made of noun classes. It was found that the Kwa systems were descended from the same ancestor as the Bantu/Bantoid ones. Some of the semantic fields coincided with each other and prefixes were similar both in phonetic shape and in meaning. CV- noun prefixes cognate with EBC ones were discovered. Extensions to verb roots have also been found in WBC – in Igbo (Emenanjo 1978) and in Degema of Edoid (Kari 2005).

Bennett and Sterk's study of 1977 also justified merging Eastern Kwa with Benue-Congo, as did Williamson's overview of (New) Benue-Congo in Bendor-Samuel 1989.

It seems to me therefore that there should be no issue here anymore and we should accept that the merger is justified. It only remains to decide what to do with Togo-Remnant, and I find no problem in suggesting that they be treated as WBC since Yoruba also has a discontinuous territory in Togo.

2.2 Central Niger – Nupoid, Ebiroid, Idomoid.

Greenberg 1963a had what one may call an Idoma group, Idoma being the first entry in his group f. However, Bennett and Sterk 1977 created a Central Niger group with a two-way split into Niger-Kaduna and Idomoid. Niger-Kaduna then split into three coordinate branches: Gade, Nupe-Gwari, and Igbiroid (= Ebiroid). Two issues are on the ground here. First is that Armstrong 1983 said that

‘... an autonomous Idomoid group does exist, forming the easternmost interface between the Kwa [WBC – BE] and the Benue-Congo languages [EBC – BE] (p. 93).

Williamson’s 1989 classification of new Benue-Congo also makes Idomoid coordinate with Nupoid. There is therefore an issue as to whether or not Idomoid and Nupoid are under Central Niger or are coordinate branches of WBC.

Second is that Bankale 2006 insists that Ebiroid is not inside Nupoid as proposed by Blench 1989. However, it is one thing to say that Ebiroid is independent of Nupoid, and quite another to say that they are coordinate at the WBC level. It appears to me that Bankale and Bennett and Sterk are in agreement that Ebiroid is not inside Nupoid. But Bankale has not removed the possibility that they are both inside Niger-Kaduna or some such node on the WBC tree.

2.3 Yoruboid-Akokoid

When the Akokoid languages were discovered at the University of Ibadan, they were christened the ‘Northern Akoko Cluster (NAK)’ (see Hoffman 1976)). Then, in the era of ‘-oid’, they were renamed Akokoid. At the time, the list included Ahan, spoken in a section of the town of Omuo-Ekiti and Ayere whose language, we now know, is called Uwu. After fieldwork there in January 2002, I quickly discovered that Ahan and the language of Ayere were close to each other, but markedly different from the rest of Akokoid. I told Kay Williamson of my finding and she said that Roger Blench had reached the same conclusion earlier. Later that year, Akinyemi 2002, although supporting Capo’s 1989 classification, provided lexicostatistic evidence which showed that the Akokoid languages scored above 80 per cent with each other while scoring between 28 and 38 with Ahan and Uwu (Ayere). His data further revealed that Ahan and Uwu scored 56 per cent with each other. Based on all this, the larger remainder of Akokoid after removing Ahan-Uwu (Ahanoid), is still called Akokoid. It includes the Oke-Agbe dialects, Arigidi, Erushu, Uro of Ajowa town, Igashi, and Oyin. Capo 1989 classifies Yoruboid and the old Akokoid as the two primary coordinate arms of his Defoid group. The issue here now is that, Capo apart, there is no study that has targeted Yoruboid and Akokoid to determine if they are sufficiently close to be considered together inside Defoid. It has to be mentioned that the languages of Akoko, in general, have borrowed massively from Yoruba.

2.4 Okoid

The classification of Oko remains an enigma. Most residents of Ogori and Mangongo speak Yoruba and Ebirá in addition to their native language. This is one reason why we should be careful how we propose a classification for Okoid. At the moment, proposals vacillate between placing Okoid inside Nupoid and making it a direct descendant of West Benue-Congo, making it coordinate with Nupoid and the others. This particular issue remains open.

2.5 Ahanoid

There is general agreement that this is different from Akokoid. There is no other group to which it even vaguely appears to belong. That means that it should be treated for now as a direct descendant of WBC, coordinate with the other recognized branches.

2.6 Akpes and the AIKA dialects

These two languages, Akpes and AIKA, are responsible for my interest in Akoko as a geographic area and the larger picture of the classification of WBC. My study of these two languages, each of them a dialect cluster, has led me to advance an Akedoid hypothesis in which Akedoid is a branch of WBC. It has three branches – Edoid (already well known and established), Akpes, and AIKA (the acronym formed for themselves by the AIKA-speaking communities. AIKA stands for Ayanran (accepted by the others as the oldest settlement, and is in Edo State), Ishe (whose dialect is called Uyegbe), Kakumo (of Ukaan fame, but whose real name is Ikaan) and Auga (whose dialect is called Iigau). I will devote the whole of the next section to an examination of this issue, starting with a picture of the controversy surrounding it.

3. AKEDOID

3.1 Earlier statements on the classification of Akpes and AIKA

Jungraithmayr 1973a, b, published short wordlists of Ishe [ĩʃɛ] (= AIKA-Ujegbe) and Oko [ɔkɔ]. Regarding Ishe, Jungraithmayr concluded (1973a: 40) that: as to its linguistic classification, no definite judgement has been possible

He added that Professor Kay Williamson in a 1970 paper affirmed that Ishe is 'very dissimilar to all surrounding languages'.

Of Oko, the language of Ogori, Jungraithmayr said (1973b: 60):

[es] laesst sich an keine der umliegenden groesseren Sprachen bzw. Dialektgruppen (Yoruba, Edo, Igbirra) anschliessen ... vergleichende Untersuchungen stehen noch aus

For reasons such as Jungraithmayr's observations, linguists and those who use the results of linguistic studies – archaeologists, ethnologists, historians, etc. – began to identify most of the languages of the area as

-- 'remnant' (Ballard 1971),
-- 'unclassified' (Hoffmann 1974), and

-- 'isolate' (Blench 1989).

As data became more available, and the AIKA noun classification system was revealed, speculation became more rampant:

-- Ohiri-Aniche 1994 (published in 1999): AIKA is more probably East Benue-Congo.

-- Blench (1994): The Ukaan language: Bantu in south-western Nigeria?

-- Connell (1998): 'Ukaan may more appropriately belong with Cross River. Further

work needs to be done to test this hypothesis' (p. 23).

--Agoyi (1997): Akpes and AIKA are part of Edoid, being two additional coordinate branches on the Edoid family tree.

In a fuller version of this work, which I hope will form part of my proposal, is a revision of the WBC tree, based, first, on my comparative study of Akpes, AIKA, and Edoid; second, on a 2006 comparative work on Nupoid and Ebiroid by Dr Tayo Bankale; and third, on Armstrong's 1983 comparative Idomoid. I propose that we merge the Akpes-AIKA node with Edoid and re-name it Akedoid, reflecting a deeper geographic extension of Edoid into Akoko-Ondo and also the fact that the Akoko arm of this new node is not part of the old Edoid. Then we split the Nupoid node into Nupoid and Ebiroid, making them each coordinate with Idomoid on a Central Niger primary branch of WBC. This still leaves Oko, which Williamson and Blench included on the Nupoid-Idomoid node. Although I am very tempted to go with them, I would rather we left Oko on its own as a branch of WBC in its own right. Although Ọkọ was not a target, I do have an Ibadan 400 word list on it, and I have access to Atoyebi 2010 as well as to his large collection of Ọkọ data. However, as far as its classification is concerned, we have to work more seriously, especially in the light of the data now available.

3.2 The sound systems of Akpes, AIKA-Ikaan and Proto-Edoid

A. Akpes

Table 1

Akpes consonant chart

Nasal		m	n			ŋ				
Plosive	p	b	t	d	c	j	k	g	kp	-
Tap/Trill			ɽ	r						
Fricative	f		s		ʃ		x			
Approximants				l		j		w		

In this Table of consonants,

c stands for [tʃ], a voiceless palato-alveolar affricate, and

j for [dʒ], a voiced palato-alveolar affricate.

[ɽ] occurs only in word-final position and is therefore an allophone of /r/.

There are seven vowels in Apes and each of them can be nasalised in the environment of a nasal consonant.

Table 2. Akpes vowels

i	u
e	o
ɛ	ɔ
a	

The tone system of Akpes is a classic ‘two tones plus downstep’ and has been described in Elugbe (2002). A high tone is marked with an acute accent ´, a low tone with a grave accent ` , and a downstep with an exclamation mark, !.

Possible syllable structures are CVC, CV, and V. In slow, deliberate speech, CVC syllables are heard as CVCV – as, for example in the name of the language: [àkpès] or [àkpèsì].

B. AIKA-Ikaan

Ikaan has a fairly rich consonant system. It is set out below

Table 3. Ikaan consonant chart

Nasal	m	n	ŋ	ŋ̃m						
(tapped)		ɲ								
Plosive	p	b	t	d	c	j	k	g	kp	gb
Tap/Trill			r							
Fricative	f	s	š	ʃ		x				
Approximants						j		w	h	
(nasalised)						j̃		w̃	h̃	

Notes on the chart:

-- This table is a systematic phonetic one. It is most likely that some of the nasal

consonants are allophones of some oral counterparts. Similarly, the nasalised approximants are definitely allophones of the oral approximants. Vowels after nasals are invariably nasalised. In our examples, nasalisation will not be marked on vowels after nasals, or on approximants before nasal vowels.

-- The contrast between c and j as well as between k and g is neutralised in word-final position where the voiced ones are devoiced. This devoicing rule also applies to r, the tap/trill.

-- In almost all cases, a word which ends in a vowel actually ends with a glottal stop. This is

so regular that I have decided it’s not crucial, especially as its absence did not seem to matter to the speakers, old or young. Secondly, both here in Ikaan and the other dialects, it appeared to be mainly limited to the elderly.

-- ɲ is a tapped alveolar nasal which is the allophone of /r/ before nasal vowels.

-- š is a breathy-voiced alveolar central fricative. Its articulation is weaker than for its voiceless counterpart.

-- l, the voiced alveolar lateral approximant, does not occur.

-- x, a voiceless velar central fricative, occurs as an allophone of /h/ before a sequence of a

close back vowel and a following one: /huV/ → hwV → [xwV]

-- c and j are tʃ and dʒ, voiceless and voiced palato-alveolar affricates, respectively.

Ikaan has a ten-vowel system with the tenth, [ə], being an allophone of /a/ in the environment of [+ATR] vowels. Thus [ə̃m] is underlyingly /ãm/ 'back'.

Table 4. AIKA-Ikaan vowels

[+ATR]		[-ATR]	
i ī	ũ u	ɪ ī	ū u
e ē	õ o	ɛ ẽ	ō ɔ
	[ə]		aã

There are closed syllables in AIKA. There are no consonant clusters. In examples such as CjV and CwV, the glide represents a close vowel which has become a glide between a C and a V.

Ikaan is a typical 'two tones plus downstep' language. In examples, non-automatic downstep will be indicated with an exclamation mark (!). Automatic downstep is, of course, not marked.

C. Proto Edoid

Table 5. Proto-Edoid consonant chart (Elugbe 1989)

NASAL						
	Lenis	mh	nh			
	Non-lenis	m	n			N (This is η in Proto-Akedoid (PAKE))
STOP						
	Implosive	ɓ	ɗ			
Plosive:						
	Lenis	ph	bh	th	dh	ch ?
				kh	gh	kph gbh
Non-lenis	p	b	t	d	c	j
			k	g	kp	gb
FRICATIVE						
		f	v			
APPROXIMANT						
				j		w

From these three consonant charts, we see that the lenis/non-lenis contrast has been lost both in Akpes and in AIKA. This does not define the two languages in any way because most Edoid languages have also lost the distinction. The voiced labiodental central fricative has also been lost both in Alpes and in AIKA. However, the putative -N- of PE has a voiced velar nasal cognate in Akpes and AIKA.

In PE, word stems were frequently of two or more syllables. In such cases, only lenis consonants were allowed in -C₂- or -C₃- position. I believe that this was inherited from Proto-Akedoid (PAKE). I have not presented a PAKE consonant chart here because it is very similar to that of PE and it is not fully reconstructed. As mentioned in the preceding paragraph, one major difference between the PAKE consonants and those of PE is the occurrence of η in PAKE.

3.3 The evidence

3.3.1 Regular sound correspondences

(1) PAKE *d in the three branches of Akedoid

- PAKE *d > *d PE
- > j Akpes
- > j AIKA-Ikaan

The development of PE *d in the Edoid languages does not involve a [j]. This is therefore a sound change peculiar to Akpes and AIKA. The only exception to this rule was before the close front unrounded *i. Supporting items: *bargain, grave, grey hair, weave*.

(2) PAKE *k

- PAKE *k > *k PE (everywhere)
- > c Akpes (before front vowels, k elsewhere)
- > c AIKA-Ikaan (c before *i, k elsewhere)

This development to [c] is found in two examples – *market* and *egg*. The other environments are supported by *fight/go to war, plant/sow, etc.*

(See the table of Akedoid consonant correspondences below.)

3.3.2 Lexical content and phonetic character

There are some lexical items which tend to be found across the length and breadth of Edoid, a rather large area. The four branches of Edoid as I have indicated already are Delta Edoid (DE), Southwestern Edoid (SWE), Northcentral Edoid (NCE), and Northwestern Edoid (NWE). Decades of contact with the Edoid languages have left me with the impression that there is a certain essence to Edoid which is reflected in part by a set of lexical items which can be used as diagnostic of Edoidness. Such words include *buy, cry/weep, doctor, earth/ground, eat, eye, fall, fight/war, hand, market, moon, mould, oil, roast, and tooth*. Kay Williamson (personal communication) pointed out that these are not Edoid innovations and so cannot be used to determine what is Edoid. I would even add that, by the same token, a language may have these items and *not* be Edoid. I accept all that. However, if a language is Edoid, not only should it have a good percentage of such items, it must also show a certain resemblance to a certain Edoid (phonetic) essence in each case. That Edoid essence introduces the element of innovation: for example, a *d* or *d* in the item 'buy' or an *o* as the stem vowel in 'weave', an *o* in the stem for 'roast', etc. This is not a rigid thing and I do not prescribe it as a new method. It just so happens that the occurrence of such items with the appropriate (edoid-type) sounds is helpful as a quick check on the possibility of the language being Edoid or not. I feel sure that those who have worked within certain groups of languages would also come to have that kind of feeling. In this case, Akpes has a good number of such items, though sometimes with slightly

more divergent phonetic shapes. AIKA on the other hand appears to have a fewer number of them. But it has a clear evidence of breathy voicing in one sound which corresponds to the same phenomenon in NWE and shares some items with Edoid which are not in Akpes. But, of course, we have to look for regular sound correspondences.

3.3.3 Lexical innovation

I have found only one lexical item without an apparent cognate elsewhere in WBC; It is 'sleep' in its verb and noun forms.

(3) 'sleep' in Akedoid

PAKE	*u-bhɪ(ŋ)chɪŋ	to sleep	*bhɪ(ŋ)chɪŋ
PE	*u-bhɪ(N)chɪN		*bhɪ(N)chɪN
Osse (NWE)			
	i-βiṛḗ (Ehueun)		birḗ
Akpes	i-mɔs		miʃ
AIKA	u-mó		(kúra)

3.3.4 Noun class prefixes

Table 6: singular/plural prefix pairing for the 'human' class in Akpes, AIKA, and Oloma

Akpes	AIKA	Oloma	English
sg. pl	sg. pl.	sg. pl.	
o-ní a-	o-ní a-	o-jò â-gbò	person
o-noó a-	o-jowés a-	â-žì ê-	man/male
o-ɲoɲo a-	o-jejen a-	â-žámhì ê-	woman/ female
o-wós a-	o-wés a-	o-víémhànhi	husband (the Oloma form means 'our husband', no plural: cf. o-viè 'ruler/priest' in Ghotuo (NCE) and Isoko (SWE))
o-ɲó a-	o-jén a-	â-žámhì ê-	wife
o-sí a-	o-šindʒ a-	i-thà --	father
o-sí a-	o-šɔ:dʒ	a-žumhinhà ê-	in-law
	a-šá:dʒ		
o-néɲa a-	o-katʃ a-	â-fá é-	guest
o-tʃa a-	o-ɲim a-	â-hjámè a-	friend
o-tú a-	o-tʃê:tʃ a-	o-ɲi pl.?	thief
i-tâ a-	e-šja a-	i-tha	very old man
o-šja a-	(AIKA-Uyegbe)		

3.3.5 The gerund and its tone

Another piece of morphological evidence comes from the gerund/verbal noun in AIKA and Edoid. It does not come from my data, but from Abiodun (2001). He

reports that

The verbal noun prefix in present-day Ukaan [AIKA – BE] alternates between

u- and ú- across the dialects (p. 290).

What is interesting here is that the prefix is invariably high-toned. In 1984, I reconstructed the gerund in PE as a discontinuous morpheme with two alternants based on [ATR] harmony, as we see in 11:

(4) The gerund morpheme in Proto-Edoid

Underlying form:	*U ... (A)mhI	
Alternants	*u ... əmhi	(if the verb stem vowel was close and [+ATR])
	*ɯ ... amni	(if the verb stem vowel was [-ATR])
[+ATR])	*u ... mhi	(if the verb stem vowel was <i>not</i> close but [-ATR])
	*ɯ ... mhi	(if the stem vowel was <i>not</i> close but [-ATR])

Its reflexes in the modern Edoid languages are shown in 10. Tonal aspects of the reflexes are shown in 7

Table 7. The gerund in the Edoid languages

DE	Degema	hir	ùhírēm	‘surrounding’
		tev	ùtévām	‘descending’
SWE	Isoko	si	èsjò	‘pulling’
		sɪ	èsjò	‘refusing’
		gbe	ègbé	‘dancing’
		dɛ	èdɛ	‘buying’
	Uvbie	mi	èmjômú	‘wringing’
		rɪ	èrjômú	‘eating’
		ru	èrwômú	‘doing’
		co	ècòomú	‘stealing’
		dɛ	èdɛmú	‘buying’
NCE	Edo	bi	ùbí!vè	‘closing’
		dɛ	ùdɛ!vè	‘buying’
		do	ùdó!vè	‘weaving’
	Yekhee (Etsako)			
	(Ekpheli)	le	úlémhì	‘eating’
		dɛ	ùdémhì	‘buying’
	(Auchi)	le	ulê	‘eating’
		dɛ	údê	‘buying’
	Ghotuo	e	ê	‘eating’
		dɛ	dê	‘buying’
NWE	Emhalhe	ri	úrímhì	‘doing’
		rɛ	úrémhì	‘eating’

Table 8. Tonal correspondences from the gerund

		prefix	stem	suffix(V)	suffix (CV)
DE	Degema	L	H	D	-
SWE	Isoko	L	H	H	-
	Uvbię L	H	L	H	
NCE	Edo	L	H	L	L
	Ekpheli	H	H	-	L
	Auchi	H	H	L	-
	Ghotuo	-	H	L	-
NWE	Emhalhe	H	H	L	L

Reconstructed PAE tones of the gerund: *H- H ... (L) L

Table 9. The gerund morpheme in AIKA

Verb	Ikaan	Iyinno	Iigau	Uyegbe	Gloss
				(Ishe)	
kón	úkón	úkún	úkón	úkón	fighting
né	úné	úné	úné	úné	defecating
kú	úkú	úkú	úkú	úkú	bathing
ńàná	únàná	únàná	únàná	únàná	buying
fìdí	ufìdí	ufìdí	ufìdí	ufìdí	entering
xwó	úxwó	úxwó	úxwó	úxwó	dying
ńièni	únjèni	únjè	únjè	únjè	urinating
wá	úwá	úwá	úwá	úwá	coming

Data from Agoyi (personal communication) show that the gerund in Akpes (for which the speakers are proposing Abesiabes as the name acceptable to all (Agoyi, personal communication)) is cognate with that which is already identified in AIKA and Edoid. It, too, has a discontinuous morpheme í ... ní . I have to take some data of my own to reach a definite conclusion on this matter. The interesting point is that partial reduplication of the verb stem is favoured in some other parts of WBC. Yoruba, for example, has wá ‘come’, wíwá ‘coming’. In Oḳo, Atoyebi (2010: 76) discusses this under ‘gerundives’ with examples including su ‘to marry’ ò-sí-su ‘(the) marrying’ and na ‘to collect’ ò-né-na ‘(the) collecting.

In Ghotuo, NCE, partial reduplication of the verb stem exists but is used for pluralisation. Igbo probably has forms of the verb with an i-/ɪ- prefix which forms what may be an infinitive, but it has no suffix element and it has no dominant tomorph that unites all verbs as we find in AIKA.

3.3.6 Lexical cognate count

The small languages of Akoko-Ondo missed out on the first real large-scale lexicostatistic classification of Benue-Kwa in Bennett and Sterk (1977). The first lexicostatistic study of Akpes and AIKA known to me is that of Ohiri-Aniche (1999).

This work was written as early as 1994 but was published as 1999. It is one of the sources cited by Williamson and Blench in support of their 2000 position on

AIKA. Her work relied heavily on lexicostatistics. She looked at small languages of the Akoko area and compared them both with each other and with the big language groups – Edoid, Igboid and Yoruboid. Her findings contain a number of inconsistencies. She said, for example, that the lexicostatistic evidence suggests that ‘... after Ikakumo [= AIKA-Ikaan – BE], the next closest relative of Akunnu [= Akpes – BE] is Edo’ (p. 87). Yet she ended up proposing that AIKA-Akpes ‘might represent an important link between the eastern and western halves of Benue-Congo’ (p. 86). In her table of cognation scores, she finds the following percentages:

(5) Ohiri-Aniche’s cognate score percentages

Note: Arigidi is Akokoid, the assumed closest relative of Yoruboid.

Arigidi-Yoruba	55
Arigidi-Igbo	45
Arigidi-Edo	41

3.3.7 Additional supporting evidence

1. The occurrence in AIKA of ɕ , a mildly breathy-voiced alveolar central fricative
2. The confirmatory role that Akpes and AIKA play with respect to PE reconstructions, in a way that other WBC languages do not.
3. Other areas that have been examined in search of supporting evidence include syllable structure. Syllable structure is basically a typological feature. But there is no doubt that the existence of closed syllables has played a part in dressing Akpes and AIKA in an aura of exoticism and possible distance from surrounding languages. Two points are worth noting here. First is that it is fairly easy to explain the source of closed syllables in Akpes and AIKA. Second is that the situation in Akpes and AIKA has happened in Degema which is in the Niger Delta, and is the farthest Edoid language from Akpes and AIKA. As with Akpes and AIKA, it is possible in Degema to recover the lost vowel. A general rule is that a final /i/ or /u/ is dropped if it has the same tone as the first stem syllable or bears a low tone.

3.3.8 Tone

Evidence from tone can be found in:

- the tone of the gerund as reconstructed for PAKE and PE;
- the loss of lexical tone on the verb as an Edoid innovation.

It should be observed that in this (gerund) form of the verb, AIKA loses tone contrast, thus showing us the route by which Edoid lost its lexical tone on verbs.

3.3.9 The role of contact

There is no doubt that contact with languages in the Akoko Area must have been responsible for some of the changes that AIKA and Akpes have undergone. From Akoko all the way to the Niger-Benue confluence, Yoruba is the lingua franca,

the surface language that prevented the linguistic world from knowing about the underlying small and endangered languages of the area. The role of Ebira should also be noted as it is active in the area through the Ebira migrant farmers. Overall, the role of contact makes comparison and reconstruction all the more important.

3.3.10 *The internal classification of Akedoid*

It is now left for us to see a classification of Edoid, Akpes and AIKA in the light of the evidence provided above.

Figure 1. Akpes and AIKA as two more co-ordinate branches of Edoid/ AKEDOID (cf. Agoyi 1997)

Figure 2. Akpes and AIKA as two arms co-ordinate with Edoid

Figure 3. Akpes and AIKA as a common earlier branch of Akedoid

At this point in time, Figure 4 best reflects my thinking. I favoured Figure 5 when I thought that some allowance should be made for the time necessary for Akpes and AIKA to remain together without Edoid. However, I am unable to find any Akpes-AIKA innovation to support Figure 5. The loss of lexical tone on

verbs is a massive Edoid innovation. The fact that Akpes and AIKA did not participate in it does not unite them: it simply shows that it happened when they were no longer with Edoid. In the tone of the gerund in AIKA, we see the situation in which lexical tones of the verb are neutralised. That must surely be the process that Edoid generalised.

4. TWO VIEWS OF THE WBC FAMILY TREE

Figure 4: Proposed WBC tree (Note: Not drawn to time or percentage scale.)

Figure 5: Proposed WBC tree2 (Note: Not drawn to time or percentage scale.)

Map 1. Draft map of West Benue-Congo

5. CONCLUSION

Any study that contradicts the Akedoid hypothesis put forward here must show that there is an alternative in which the evidence is stronger than what I have presented. I have not yet found a WBC group that can be related to Akpes and AIKA in the way that I have found it for Edoid. The onus is on fellow workers in the field of classification through comparison and reconstruction to show that they have different data that credibly contradict my proposal.

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